

Deliverable

D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1.1

Data Management Plan

June 30, 2020

Workpackage 1 of

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES

Responsible Partner: SSI

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JRP Deliverable	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1.1 Data Management Plan
Join Research Project	JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES
JRP Leader	Pikka Jokelainen, SSI
Other contributors	TOXOSOURCES Consortium
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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>This is the default setting. If this deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders / Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s): TOXOSOURCES Consortium, DMP group on the OHEJP website

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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Background

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-toxosources/>)

TOXOSOURCES is a 2.5-year Joint Research Project of the One Health EJP that focuses on *Toxoplasma gondii* at the interface of humans, animals, food, and environment. TOXOSOURCES Consortium comprises 20 One Health EJP partners and several external partners.

Project Leader and DMP contact person: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, PIJO@ssi.dk

Work Package:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1 Coordination and impact

Task:

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1-T1 Management, coordination and communication

Aim and focus, specific considerations

Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of data management during a project. It covers the life cycle of the data from collection to availability and long-term storage. TOXOSOURCES DMP is a living document that will cover the relevant aspects of the many types of data that are collected and generated during the project.

TOXOSOURCES will do its best to make the research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR-principle). Ethical considerations, GDPR, data security and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are considered along the process. Linking with the One Health Outcome Inventory (OHOI) is utilized. In addition to the components of the FAIR-principle, transparency and visibility are also emphasized. Moreover, as the project is about One Health, inter-disciplinary interoperability is important, and keywords need to cover those used in several fields.

Process and format

The process of developing DMP of TOXOSOURCES started already at proposal writing stage. The list of data covered in TOXOSOURCES DMP is specified and updated during the project, and management of the data is discussed proactively. DMP is regularly discussed with the TOXOSOURCES-WP-leaders and with the TOXOSOURCES Consortium during the project.

This deliverable is the backbone of the DMP; the DMP itself will be compiled using a specific tool provided by the OHEJP: Collaborative Data Platform (DCP). At the time of preparing this deliverable, the tool is not yet available.

Resources

TOXOSOURCES Project Leader is responsible of the TOXOSOURCES DMP and has allocated time for developing, compiling and updating it. TOXOSOURCES Project Leader participates in DMP Committee of the OHEJP. Resources have been earmarked for publishing Gold open access.

Examples of data covered in TOXOSOURCES DMP

The list of data covered in TOXOSOURCES DMP is specified and updated during the project. The details will be included in the DMP when the tool is available. Examples of types of data already discussed include:

- Lists of records identified and data extracted in the process of systematic reviews
Made available as supplementary file to publications and/or project deliverables. These are uploaded to Zenodo.
- Questionnaires
Made available as supplementary files to publications and/or project deliverables. These are uploaded to Zenodo.
- Models
The QMRA models from WP2 will be made available via a repository (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip/>).
- Sequence data
We are looking into suitable options for the sequence data from WP5. Metadata and keywords will be discussed.
- Methods
SOPs (WP3, WP4, WP5) are public project deliverables. These are uploaded to Zenodo.
- Scientific articles
Scientific article manuscripts are made available in preprint servers when considered useful, and articles are published Gold open access.